

Consiglio Nazionale
delle Ricerche

Mendeleev's Garden

- Fully available
- Limited availability, future risk to supply
- Rising threat from increased use
- Serious threat in the next 100 years
- Synthetic element
- ☢ Radioactive
- From conflict areas

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